

MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE STRATEGY FOR IMPROVING TOURISM CAPACITY

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Abstract: . The article presents proposals aimed at improving the effective management system in the tourism sector based on strategy and tactics, and increasing the effectiveness of using human resources as a general business strategy in the tourism industry in the long term.

Keywords. Effective management in tourism , tourism industry, strategic planning , economic development, resources , tourism policy .

An effective management system in the tourism sector can be improved based on strategy and tactics. In the tourism industry, in the long term, there is an increasing focus on improving the efficiency of using human resources as a general business strategy. Strategy is necessary to accurately predict the future, which is the art of studying the future, analyzing various scenarios, and an idea that will give an advantage in the future competition.

In tourism, strategic planning is carried out on the basis of a strategy. It mainly consists in choosing the main goals of the tourist company's activities, aimed at determining the final results to be achieved, taking into account the means and methods of achieving the set goals and providing the necessary resources. The principle of long-term planning is from the past to the future, and strategic planning is from the future to the present, therefore the developed strategies show the impact of the future on today's decisions.

Strategy (from the Greek “ *strategos* ”) literally means “the art of a general with special powers”, and when translated into civilian language, it means the art of high leadership. Strategist is a leader with high powers. According to I. Ansoff, strategy, in essence, represents a set of rules for making decisions in managing an organization's activities. In the current era, the strategy of an enterprise determines the goals, means and limits of its possible actions.

If we turn to the concept of "strategy", we find its interpretation in various meanings in the current literature. For example, in some cases, the strategy is used in the sense of developing a long-term goal, that is, a comprehensive planning in a broad sense, divided into parts, aimed at achieving the goal and ensuring its organization. The following three stages of the concept in the works of BS Zhikharevitch can serve as an example of a widespread view of studying the essence of the strategy at the city level:

- firstly, an economic strategy (strategy in the narrow sense) is a set of documents on measures and resources that will help bring the future state of the city's economy closer to the desired state of the city's economy as desired by city leaders .

- secondly, the strategic plan for economic development is a set of documents, a strategic program, which includes a block of documents and a two-year plan of measures that develops an economic strategy that implements the concept of economic policy of local government departments.

- thirdly, the economic strategy as a process is a system of documents on strategic management. They are considered as a set of organizational systems and processes, which are

clear, constantly reproducing schemes that implement the economic strategy of the city and ensure the implementation of strategic goals and objectives.

If we analyze the above definitions of economic strategy as a predictive-analytical document, the definition of economic strategy and strategic plan of economic development fully coincide with the definition of the concept of economic development considered above. Thus, these categories are very close to each other, and the use of the definition of “strategic plan” is fully justified.

In our opinion, it is necessary and expedient to draw up a long-term strategic plan for tourism development, since it is the result of the strategic planning process, and the implementation of the current strategy is achieved through annual plans - forecasts and targeted problem programs. Considering the strategic plan as the main document of the strategic planning system, it can be considered as the main component of strategic management for the development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan, that is, for the entire country and for a separate entity.

In order to clarify the relationship between the concepts of “strategy” and “strategic plan”, we will try to determine the meaning of strategy as reflected in the works of the famous classics of strategic planning I. Ansoff, R. Akoff, W. King, D. Cleland, G. Koons and S. Donnell. I. Ansoff defines strategy as “a set of rules that an organization uses to make decisions during its activities” In this case, strategy can be seen as a means of achieving future goals. Other definitions are close to these ideas and are described in the literature on this issue. Thus, the categories of "strategy" and "strategic plan" can be considered as a whole and a part of it, depending on the state of their interdependence, that is, in other words, it is appropriate for a strategic plan to include the main aspects of the strategy in its composition.

The state's tourism policy is based on strategy and tactics. Strategy is understood as a method of using means and general directions to achieve a set goal. It allows you to group actions aimed at solving the task set, excluding all other options, without negating the adopted strategy. Tourism strategy determines the state's activities in the field of tourism development and reorganization. This activity is primarily aimed at developing targeted programs and a general concept of development, the implementation of which requires time and significant financial resources. Tactics are understood as someone's course of action, in which a method of achieving a certain goal is chosen. Tourism tactics are methods and specific measures to achieve a set goal in specific conditions (for example, the procedure for licensing international tourism activities, pricing and taxation in tourism). The purpose of tourism tactics is to choose the most optimal solution in a given economic situation.

Tourism strategy and tactics are widely used to increase efficiency in tourism. First of all, a strategy is needed to accurately predict the future. Strategy is the art of studying the future, analyzing various scenarios, and is an important idea that gives hotels an advantage in the competitive struggle in the future.

In order to diversify tourism products and services aimed at various segments of the tourism market in our republic, further increase their competitiveness, create an acceptable and convenient environment for domestic and international pilgrimage tourism, expand transport routes, improve the quality of transport services, widely promote tourism products, and also strengthen the image of our country as a safe destination for travel and recreation, the following will be implemented:

- During the celebration of the national holiday of Navruz, Independence Day and New Year's Day, as well as the religious holidays of Eid al-Fitr and Eid al-Adha, additional and transferable days off are set for a period of no less than three days;

- a system of “family travel leave” of no less than five working days will be introduced, which provides for joint travel with parents, relatives, elders and teachers. In this case, “family travel leave” will be provided at the expense of the annual basic leave and will be implemented with the consent of the employer in accordance with collective agreements;

- Starting from March 1, 2021, a tourist (hotel) fee will be collected from citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan and stateless persons permanently residing in the Republic of Uzbekistan for each day of their stay in accommodation facilities in the amount determined by the Cabinet of Ministers. In this case, the tourist (hotel) fee will be directed to financing measures aimed at promoting and encouraging domestic tourism and ensuring the occupancy of accommodation facilities during the low tourist season;

- flights of foreign airlines to the Republic of Uzbekistan, aimed at organizing trips of foreign tourists from Indonesia, Bangladesh and Malaysia to the Republic of Uzbekistan and within the framework of the "Umra+" program, will be carried out without hindrance, except for the safety rules of landing and take-off;

- information aimed at widely promoting the republic's tourist attractions, familiarizing citizens with the rich natural, cultural and historical heritage, and popularizing domestic tourism (not pursuing commercial goals) is equated with information on issues of spirituality and enlightenment.

These events It is also a program of measures to form the flow of tourists in our republic and create the necessary conditions for them .

The tourism development strategy includes strategic goals, expected indicators, work and monitoring programs. The implementation of the measures specified in this strategy will contribute to the transition of the tourism sector to an active growth cycle, increasing its competitiveness at the national and international levels. With the implementation of the adopted program in the tourism sector, the tourism services provided will continue to develop and expand based on market laws. The successful implementation of the tourism strategy depends on the active participation of the responsible organization and representatives of the local tourism business in achieving the set strategic goals, in a mutually agreed manner.

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